

Photothermal Initiation of Frontal Polymerization in Additive Manufacturing of Discontinuous Fiber-reinforced Thermoset Composites

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Challenges in Composite Manufacturing

Boeing autoclave

Heated mold for manufacturing a wind blade

Frontal Polymerization (FP)

Self-propagative exothermic reaction wave driven by heat of polymerization

3D Printing via Frontal Polymerization

- Rapid curing of thermoset composites during 3D printing processes
- Freeform and layer-by-layer printing enabled by synchronized and asynchronous frontal curing

Activation of Frontal Reaction

Frontal polymerization is typically activated using thermal contact methods

- Long activation times (few seconds to minutes)
- Local variation in material properties or damage to material

Activate frontal polymerization remotely

Photothermal Activation

- Photothermal activation offers
 - Remote initiation
 - Precise control of energy input

- Exploit high absorptivity of carbon fibers
 - Blue laser light source (wavelength = 450 nm)

Rapid Initiation of Frontal Reaction

- Frontal activation within 200 ms

FP Initiation During Composite Printing

Rapid, remote initiation of frontal polymerization during direct ink writing (DIW) of carbon fiber composites

Effect of Material and Processing Parameters

Initiation time of FP can be tuned by varying the material and processing parameters

FP initiation in < 1s using various concentrations of milled carbon fibers

Multipoint Initiation

Overall cure time can be reduced by applying multiple laser pulses

Conclusions

- Low-power laser enables rapid, remote initiation of FP during DIW of thermoset composites
- Reliable initiation achieved with as little as 0.1 vol% carbon fiber for photothermal conversion
- Automated laser integration allows multipoint initiation, significantly reducing layer cure times
- Compatible with diverse FP resin systems and fiber reinforcements
- Supports spatially controlled, on-demand curing for manufacturing freeform, unsupported, and complex multi-layer structures